

SMARTPHONE USAGE: ITS IMPACT ON CLASSROOM BEHAVIOR OF THE STUDENTS AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY SULU SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This research examines the relationship between smartphone use and students' academic behavior, looking at the negative impact of the smartphone with the goal of offering insights on how to minimize the negative impact of smartphone usage. The researchers aimed to look at how using smartphones affects student's learning. It wants to see how often the students spend the use of smartphones impacting their academic behavior. The survey included questions on the frequency of smartphone use, the time spent on different statements and perceived impact in academic performance. The quantitative data were analyzed using statistical methods such as median and Kruskal-Wallis to identify the relationship between smartphone and academic behavior of the students. The results have surfaced that the time spent using smartphones has moderately impacted their academic behavior. Also, the results of classroom behaviors imposed by the grade 12 students, agreed that the statements of the researchers that provided have a negative impact on their classroom behavior. In conclusion, smartphone usage has a negative impact on the classroom behavior of the students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School.

Keywords: *Smartphone Usage, Classroom Behavior, Time Spent.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, smartphones have become ubiquitous, transforming from mere communication tools to multifaceted devices that serve as gateways to information, entertainment, and social interaction. While the integration of smartphones into everyday life has brought numerous benefits, their usage in classroom settings has raised growing concerns among educators, parents, and researchers. The increasing presence of smartphones in educational environments has posed significant implications on students' classroom behavior and overall academic performance. The pervasive nature of these devices often leads to distraction, reduced attention spans, and a decline in face-to-face interactions, affecting both learning outcomes and social development.

The researchers have personally observed the disruptive effects of smartphone usage in the classroom. It is not uncommon for students to be tempted to check social media, play games, or engage in other non-academic activities during lessons. These behaviors result in reduced attention to instructional content and lower participation in class discussions. While it is undeniable that smartphones have practical academic uses—such as accessing e-books, online research, and educational apps—they also serve as constant sources of distraction. The researchers aim to investigate: how does smartphone usage impact students' behavior in the classroom?

Gardiner (2016) emphasized the intensity of this phenomenon, stating, "The student's cellphone addiction is no joke." He further elaborated that smartphone can dominate students' focus entirely—when the phone is visible, students are engrossed by it, and when it is hidden away, they feel anxious due to its absence. This compulsive attachment indicates an emotional dependency that can interfere with learning and attentiveness. Similarly, Fisayo et.al., (2022) noted that student cellphone use has been associated with poorer learning outcomes, likely due to heightened distraction levels. Their study explored how cellphone-related anxiety and addiction could disrupt classroom learning, emphasizing the need for educational policies to mitigate negative impacts.

Smartphones have deeply embedded themselves in our daily routines to the extent that, for many individuals, they are the first object seen upon waking and the last before sleeping (Borger et.al., 2019). Children and adolescents now commonly own smartphones, often using them without restrictions, which increases their risk of developing addictive behaviors (Fischer-Grote et. al., 2019). The unchecked use of smartphones can lead to social isolation. Students may neglect real-time, face-to-face interactions, which hinders their ability to build interpersonal relationships, work collaboratively, and develop essential social skills.

Mahsud et al. (2020) discussed how the excessive use of smartphones in classrooms disrupts students' focus and learning. They examined cultural groups to assess levels of attention and anxiety, concluding that smartphones significantly impair concentration. In the researchers' own observations, excessive smartphone usage has been linked to several negative classroom behaviors. Many students, especially those unable to regulate their smartphone habits, demonstrated poor academic performance

and disengagement from class activities. The researchers are therefore compelled to explore whether smartphone usage has a predominantly negative or potentially positive impact on student behavior in academic settings.

Karabatak et al. (2021) also explored smartphone usage among university students, analyzing factors such as frequency of use, purpose, and demographic influences. Their findings revealed complex relationships between smartphone habits and classroom engagement.

Ramazanoglu et al. (2020) investigated the links between smartphone addiction, internet dependency, and social media use among high school students. Using quantitative methods, they concluded that these interrelated behaviors contribute significantly to student distraction. Similarly, Thomas (2020) examined the frequency of smartphone usage among school principals and its relationship to job satisfaction. His study utilized Pearson's correlation coefficient and descriptive statistics, emphasizing that even educational leaders are not immune to the psychological effects of smartphone overuse.

Wacks and Weinstein (2021) provided an alarming overview of the health consequences of excessive smartphone usage. They linked it to a variety of disorders such as depression, anxiety, obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), ADHD, and even alcohol use disorder. These mental health concerns can impair students' ability to regulate emotions, focus on tasks, and perform academically. Other reported issues include sleep disturbances, diminished physical fitness, poor eating habits, and changes in brain structure. This underscores the urgency for educators and health professionals to acknowledge and address the multifaceted consequences of excessive smartphone use.

Huang et al. (2022) studied 439 college students to determine correlations between smartphone use and suicidal ideation. The results showed that students who used smartphones for more than five hours a day were more likely to experience depressive symptoms and thoughts of suicide. The analysis revealed that these mental health issues were exacerbated by lower levels of social support and excessive digital engagement. These findings further illustrate the psychological toll of unchecked smartphone use.

A meta-analysis by Sunday et al. (2021) revealed that smartphone addiction negatively affects learning and academic performance. The analysis demonstrated that the more a student used a smartphone during study sessions, the more their cognitive functions and academic achievements declined. Skills essential for academic success, such as critical thinking, time management, and memory retention, were adversely impacted. Cha et al. (2018) studied middle school students in South Korea and found that the main predictive factors for smartphone addiction included the duration of daily smartphone use and time spent on social networking services. These patterns suggest that behavioral interventions may be necessary to curb problematic smartphone use among adolescents.

In addition to its psychological and cognitive effects, smartphone usage also influences students' classroom behaviors. Pan et al. (2024) examined the digital transformation in higher education and how it affects student learning behaviors in China. Their study revealed that students' attitudes toward digital learning significantly influence their engagement and academic habits. Meanwhile, Shakoor et al. (2021) provided evidence from Pakistan indicating a dual impact: while smartphones can facilitate access to learning resources, their misuse contributes to behavioral problems and decreased performance.

Barreras (2024) explored how smartphone usage affects students' sense of social integration. Rather than merely serving as tools for connection, smartphones have become essential to how students perceive their interactions with peers. Excessive use can either strengthen or weaken social bonds, depending on how they are used. Similarly, Razzaq et al. (2018) highlighted the role of smartphone habits, internet literacy, and mobile learning in fostering students' self-efficacy—students' belief in their ability to use smartphones for educational purposes. Their findings suggested that when used effectively, smartphones could be a valuable asset for learning.

Despite these potential benefits, the overall concern remains: Are students truly benefiting from their access to smartphones in the classroom, or are they succumbing to the distractions these devices present? The researchers of this study aim to determine whether smartphone usage exerts a positive or negative influence on student behavior in the classroom. By examining various dimensions—academic performance, social interaction, attention span, and psychological well-being—this study seeks to offer a comprehensive analysis of how smartphones affect the modern learning environment.

Research Questions

This study focused on the smartphone usage and its impact on the classroom behavior of the students. Thus, the following were the guided research questions:

1. What is the level of smart phone usage of students in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School?
2. What are the classroom behaviors imposed by students?
3. Is there an impact of smartphone usage to classroom behavior?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers used the correlational method in this study. According to Bhandari (2021) a correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them, and correlation reflects the strength and/or direction of the relationship between two (or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative.

Research Site

This study was conducted at Mindanao state university – Sulu Senior High School department. There are two buildings for senior high school; the admin building is located between the College of Agriculture and College of Arts and Sciences Buildings while the main building is located near the gymnasium, in front of University Cafeteria. The said university is about 2 kilometers away from the town of Jolo and is located beside the Provincial Office of Sulu.

Research Instrument

In this study, the researchers were used adapted A survey questionnaire to gather data from the respondents. The following are the references of the questionnaire; Hossain (2019), Bautista (2020), and Viola (2021). The questionnaire is composed of two parts; the first part of the questionnaire conducts by the researcher by surveying the respondents of how many hours they spent on using a smart phone, for the second part of questionnaire is classroom behavior of students as affected by use of smartphone which compose of 11 statements and to be rated using Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neither Agree or Disagree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). And the result of S-CVI/Ave was 0.8 while the total agreement is 7 and for the S-CVI/UA were 0.46. for the reliability test the result was. 826

Respondents

The respondents of the study were 280 Senior High School students from Mindanao State University Sulu. It was selected through stratified random sampling to ensure representation across GAS and STEM strand. According to Parsons (2017), Stratified random sampling is a sampling method in which a few groupings, or strata, are formed from various combinations of attributes in the study population, and a certain number of individuals belonging to each group are sampled. Table 1 below illustrates the number of respondents in each section.

Table 1. Representation of the Sample Size in every Section

Sections	Population	Sample
STEM 1-12	79	22
STEM 2-12	81	22
STEM 3-12	78	22
STEM 4-12	76	21
STEM 5-12	83	23
STEM 6-12	82	22
GAS 1-12	74	20
GAS 2-12	75	20

GAS 3-12	75	20
GAS 4-12	75	21
GAS 5-12	80	22
GAS 6-12	83	23
GAS 7-12	81	22
TOTAL	1022	280

Data Collection

The researchers obtained permission by sending letters to the Mindanao State University-sulu Director to conduct this study. The researchers also asked permission from the respective advisers of the grade 12 students both STEM and GAS strand to manage the survey in their classes. After the permission is being granted, the researchers introduced the research to the respondents, explained the questionnaire's directions, and distributed the questionnaire. The respondents were given 5 minutes to answer the questionnaire, and it was collected immediately after the completion.

Statistical Techniques

The researchers used median to determine the level of smart phone usage of students in Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School, and to determine the classroom behaviors imposed by students. Kruskal- Wallis test was used to assess the impact of smart phone usage to classroom behavior.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2. Optimism Level of Smartphone Usage

Time Spent	Frequency	Percent	Median	Description
1-3 hours	93	33.2		Light users
4-6 hours	84	30.0	2.0	Moderate users
7 and more hours	103	36.8		Heavy users
Total	280	100.0		

Note: 1(1-3) =Light users, 2(4-6) = Moderate users, 3(7 and more) = Heavy users.
Source: Pawar (2024).

Table 2 the time spent using smartphones. As shown in the table above the frequency of 1-3 hours (light users) is 93, 4-6 hours (moderate users) is 84, and 103 for 7 and more (heavy users), total of 280, the level of smartphone usage is light users,

moderate users and heavy users. The classification of smartphone usage levels into light, moderate, and heavy users follows common categorizations in contemporary literature (Samaha & Hawi, 2016)

Table 3. Smartphone Usage Effects on Classroom Behavior

Statement	Md	Description
1. The use of smartphones distracts students' learning in general.	4.0	Agree
2. Smartphones cause students to do less schoolwork.	4.0	Agree
3. Smartphones can cause a lack of sleep which affects their behavior in class.	4.0	Agree
4. Smartphone usage can disrupt the students' participation.	4.0	Agree
5. Smartphones have negatively impacted students' moral values.	4.0	Agree
6. Smartphones prevent me from completing my tasks efficiently inside the classroom.	4.0	Agree
7. Smartphones lessen the student's ability to concentrate and think deeply or creatively.	4.0	Agree
8. Having a hard time concentrating in class while doing assignments or working due to smartphone use.	4.0	Agree
9. Smartphone usage can disturb the students' concentration.	4.0	Agree
10. Students may become addicted to the constant connection of smartphones which can negatively impact their academic environment.	4.0	Agree
11. Students' usage can lessen students' listening habit.	4.0	Agree

Table 3 presents the classroom behaviors imposed by the grade 12 students at Mindanao State University- Senior High School responses are measured using a median (Md) score, where the interpretation ranges from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5). The students agreed to all the statements given by the researcher. The overall grand median score of 4.0 indicates a Agree level among students. This suggests that smartphone usage has a negative impact on the academic behavior of the students.

The results were consistent with findings from recent studies on smartphone use and its effects on academic performance and classroom engagement (Lepp et al., 2015; Samaha & Hawi, 2016; Hawi & Samaha, 2017).

Table 4. Kruskal Wallis test to compare the Smartphone Usage Effects to Classroom Behavior based on Time Spent.

Time spent	1-3 hours		4-6 hours		7 or more hours		$X^2 (2)$	$p - Value$
Classroom behavior	N	Mean Rank	N	Mean rank	N	Mean Rank	1.879	.391
	93	1.33.70	84	150.07	103	138.83		

Table 4 presents the results of a Kruskal-Wallis H test conducted to determine whether there are statistically significant differences in classroom behavior based on the duration of smartphone usage among students. The participants were grouped according to their reported daily smartphone usage: 1–3 hours, 4–6 hours, and 7 or more hours. The test revealed no statistically significant differences in classroom behavior among the groups, $\chi^2(2) = 1.879$, $p = .391$. This indicates that the amount of time students spent using smartphones did not significantly influence their classroom behavior.

These findings are consistent with the study of Lepp et al. (2015), who noted that while excessive smartphone usage may be associated with various academic and behavioral concerns, the direct relationship with classroom behavior is often influenced by other contextual and individual factors, such as self-regulation, classroom environment, and instructional strategies. Similarly, Kuznekoff and Titsworth (2013) suggested that the content and context of smartphone usage—rather than mere duration—play a more critical role in shaping student behavior and academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers conclude that majority of the respondents use their smartphone for about 7 and more hours which corresponds to heavy users. This suggest that students spent most of their time on using smartphone.

Additionally, students agreed that the use of smartphone have negatively impact the classroom behavior of the students where in the students believe that the use of smartphones distracts students' learning in general, also smartphones can cause a lack of sleep which affects their behavior in class and students may also become addicted to the constant connection of smartphones which can negatively impact their academic environment. so, it means that smartphone usage really does affect their behavior in class negatively.

The researchers also used the Kruskal-Wallis test to confirmed that there is no significant difference in the impact of smartphone usage to classroom behavior when classified according to time spent.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend the following:

Research Agenda

1. To the students, control your phone use, set limits for your phone each day and use apps to help you track your time and stay within your limits. Do not let your phone control you, you control your phone.
2. The teachers should set classroom rules, rules for smartphone use in the room, such as keeping phones during lessons and just use it only for educational purposes.
3. The parents should always keep an eye on their children and make rules about phone use at home, like screen time limits and when phones should be put away during bedtime or if is not needed, be consistent with this rule.
4. The school administrator should train digital citizenship, train students about responsible technology use and online safety.
5. The future researchers should look deeper into knowing the long-term impact of smartphone usage, conduct longitudinal studies to understand the long-term effects of smartphone addiction on academic performance, mental health, and overall well-being. This will help them understand the lasting consequences of excessive smartphone use and develop more effective interventions.

Research Problem

1. Correlation between smartphone use and over all classroom behavior
2. Impact of smartphone use in specific classroom behaviors
3. Difference in smartphone use and classroom behavior across students' characteristics

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Researchers set guidelines and principles to ensure that the participants were informed about the study's purpose, topic, and their role in the research process. It includes explaining the questionnaire and how their response will be used, and providing participants with information about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The aim of the research ethics protocol is to promote the responsible conduct of research and to protect the rights and interests of the participants. The researchers secured all the information with confidentiality and by not disclosing the identity of the respondents.

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